

Demonstrating CLUE - AI applications for on-board FDIR and prognostics for constellations

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Constellations require complex operations and must ensure high service reliability. In addition, the large number of satellites in orbit requires the use of strategies to reduce the risk of space debris towards the zero-debris goal promoted by ESA. These aspects make autonomy and improvement of the on-board FDIR system one of the most urgent developments to reduce operational costs and response time to unexpected events. This paper illustrates the results of some applications of CLUE to enhance on-board FDIR and prognostics for constellations. CLUE is a customizable software solution for predictive diagnostics, troubleshooting support and on-board prognostics developed by SATE, based on the selected use of artificial intelligence, with an approach that aims at rapid system configuration and validation for the entire constellation. The workflow for using CLUE includes hybrid on-board and on-ground deployment, system reconfigurability, and the evolving role of the “human in the loop”.

1 Introduction

Constellations operations are becoming more and more complex and require highly automated tasks to handle the variety of operative conditions and events, while granting the required service availability. Increasing with the number of satellites, the massive amounts of data collected can be used to extract new knowledge to define operations improvements and bring more autonomy on-board. Leveraging the knowledge already available and combining it with data-driven approaches can provide major benefits to operations and on-board autonomy. This is particularly true for on-board FDIR tasks and lifetime prediction of components, which is important to enable a condition-based decision-making approach to constellation management and End of Life disposal. In a large satellites constellation scenario, the similarity among satellites sharing the same design and components can be exploited to extract models of their typical behaviour from historical data. These typical be-

haviour models combined with additional knowledge-based and data-based approaches can be used as reference for detecting deviations and checking the health status of the whole constellation, identifying known and unknown anomalies and their expected evolution along time. This paper presents the results of a project carried out by SATE and OHB System under ESA contract, to demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of the use of SATE CLUE modules for on-board predictive diagnostics and prognostics [1], based on the selected use of artificial intelligence, with an approach that aims at rapid system configuration and validation for the entire constellation.

2 Methodology

A variety of ML methodologies have been defined and investigated in the field of fault diagnostics and prognostics, including Shallow Neural Network, Deep Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, k-nearest neighbour, Naïve Bayes, Random Forest [2] [3] [4] [5] [6]. Using AI-based methods can be very powerful to allow the detection of several types of (known and unknown) anomalies under various operational contexts. In fact, the increasing complexity of space systems requires a shift from traditional ‘out-of-limit threshold’ checks, because these are not capable of detecting subtle or subsystem interdependent anomalies, which become even more important in distributed systems such as constellations. However, AI/ML requires enough data to properly characterise recurrent anomaly patterns (or fault modes), if available, but also an approach that allows for the detection of anomalies that may have never occurred before. In this regard, some key issues have to be faced:

- the lack of suitable OPS data temporal resolution for algorithms training on ground
- the need for a FDIR that is robust to the variability of the satellite operational contexts, which

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may not all be tested or simulated during the mission preparation

- the enhanced FDIR systems shall be effective under both recurrent and new types of anomalies/failures

The approaches considered shall target re-usability and generality of the models from the point of view of the type of anomaly detectable, the related subsystem and the mission.

The solution proposed in this project is designed to overcome the above limitations. The diagnostics and prognostics approach exploits the CLUE modules that implement advanced techniques exploiting Machine Learning to improve current FDIR systems in terms of:

- Early detection of incipient faults
- Early identification of possible root causes
- Identification of multiple unrelated yet concurrent faults
- Time to failure prediction

The CLUE library collects a variety of approaches developed by SATE for different industrial applications, which make selected use of artificial intelligence depending on the use case and engineering knowledge available. In fact, the CLUE library includes context-based data-driven anomaly detection methods and correlation analyses applicable to the whole telemetry parameters, as well as approaches based on Machine Learning models that exploit the engineering knowledge available on the monitored system to extract subsystems-specific models, enabling more accurate root cause detection. All these approaches provide highly interpretable and reconfigurable solutions to adapt to different mission phases. During the configuration phase, the most suitable approach for the use case is selected and trained.

In the present study, the approach used was based on I/O Neural Networks modelling the nominal behaviour of the components of interest, as described in the next section. In this approach, the health index is based on the comparison between a measured variable and its estimate provided by a the model (such as Neural Networks). The dynamic analysis of this deviation allows identifying early symptoms of changes in the behaviour of the monitored system that could be associated to incipient faults.

The output produced by the on-board system equipped with this solution consists of health indexes of each monitored component, alerts triggers with associated most likely root cause of the anomaly, estimate of the Remaining time to Failure. Several other

auxiliary data are produced that can be delivered to ground in support to investigation of events.

Figure 1: CLUE library main modules and output.

The RUL estimate is based on advanced Health index processing and trend analysis techniques to predict the time at which it will reach critical values, typically associated to failure conditions.

In a constellation scenario, CLUE algorithms can be trained and configured based on data of few example satellites of the constellation, and then used over the whole fleet, or subsets of satellites sharing similar design and data profiles. For example, satellites belonging to different orbital planes may need specific configurations, depending on the monitored component. Simulation data can also be used to extract a first configuration of the models to be further adjusted in the validation phase prior deployment to the whole constellation. With this approach, when new satellites are launched, they can be monitored as soon as they are flying, with no need to collect months of data for models training.

Figure 2: CLUE configuration based on few satellites, validation and deployment for the whole constellation.

3 Use case

The project addressed the AOCS subsystem as a first use case to show the capabilities and performance of

the proposed approach, with particular focus on Reaction Wheels components, their typical failures being identified as:

- Reaction wheel (RW) bearing degradation
- Reaction wheel bearing temperature sensor failure
- Reaction wheel electronics failure

The input processed by the on-board modules include satellite housekeeping parameters, as well as derived parameters computed from the existing telemetry. A subset of relevant telemetries was selected to train the I/O Neural Network based CLUE approach to characterise the expected nominal behaviour of the above components, including current, power, RW speed, temperatures.

It is highlighted that the approach implemented does not use the friction torque estimate available on-board, which is used by the standard FDIR by fixed threshold checking to detect wheels bearings degradation.

The expected benefits from the application derive from the following considerations:

- The Reaction Wheel performances can have significant impact on the S/C pointing accuracy. Early detection of Anomalies related to Reaction wheel assemblies (RWAs), being main actuators for the SC attitude control, can prevent the risk of having degraded performances.
- In the case of an anomaly leading to a reconfiguration of the RWA, proper anticipation to the failure allows performing this reconfiguration in a controlled scenario, preventing unwanted reconfigurations during critical SC manoeuvres, which could ultimately impact the service availability.

The on-board execution of the monitoring allows accessing all sampled telemetries from all subsystems at maximum sampling rate, which may be necessary to properly characterise the behaviour of these components and detect early symptoms of malfunctions.

4 Testbed implementation

The project was focused mainly on proving the benefits from the use of the proposed approach to enhance the on-board FDIR and prognostics capabilities. Nevertheless, the activity also included the demonstration of the customised CLUE modules on a representative HW platform, to measure required computational resources and assess feasibility in in-board applications. The board selected for the implementation of

the testbed is the LS1046A-RDB by NXP, which shares the same processor as Beyond Gravity Lynx board.

In the tests execution, a same core hosts the execution of the Linux OS, running with pre-emption, and the CLUE static library. Although this scenario is not representative of the flight one, it is deemed sufficient to assess the resource requirements, considering that the CLUE software has no dependencies on the OS or other external libraries, as it is self-contained C code. The testbed demonstration showed that processor performances in the range of >150 DMIPS would be sufficient to meet the performances reported for the proposed solution.

5 Test results

This section presents the results of the tests carried out with the customized module for the AOCS use case to assess performance and benefits over the current FDIR approach, which is based on fixed threshold checking of temperatures and friction torque (estimated onboard).

The data used for the tests were generated by OHB System high-fidelity simulation block, which implements a mathematical model to represent the performance and functionality of a reaction wheel, while emulating its real interface. The model was adjusted to allow artificial fault injection, reproducing a realistic mission profile and data. The generated datasets are the following:

- Nominal data
- Failure type F0 - friction offset injected
- Failure type F1 - friction step increase injected
- Failure type F2 - friction drift injected
- Failure type F3 – electronics failure (wrong commanded torque)
- Failure type F4 - temperature sensor failure (short and open circuit)

A subset of the nominal data were used for the training of the fault detection module. The other nominal data, covering a variety of operative conditions (simulating also different ranges of variation of speed and temperatures) and ageing conditions of the reaction wheel, were used for the tests. In total, about 2000 orbits were simulated by OHB under the various nominal and failure conditions. Of these, 500 were used for training/configuration of the modules, the remaining ones for the performance validation tests. The **Table 1** reports the KPIs measured over the test data.

Here follows an example of the result of the CLUE

Name	Meaning	Test outcome	Target
Precision positive	Among all CLUE alerts, how many are correct	98.5%	>99%
Precision false	Among all CLUE alerts, how many are incorrect	1.5%	<1%
Recall positive	Among all cases with off-nominal conditions how many are correctly identified by CLUE alert	98.2%	>90%
Recall negative	Among all nominal cases how many are correctly identified by CLUE	90.5%	none
Missed standard FDIR alerts	Among all correct CLUE alerts how many are not detected by standard FDIR	82.1%	none
Early detection	Time interval between an alert by the CLUE system and a real component failure (excluding crash breaking events) or standard FDIR alert	15 to 50 days	>10 hours
Fault Isolation Module accuracy	Among all CLUE alerts, how many are given with the correct failure mode information: mechanical (bearing) failure (F0, F1 and F2), electronics failure (F3), defective thermistor (F4).	99.6%	>99%
RUL estimate accuracy	Percentage accuracy of the CLUE RUL estimate given at the time of the 1st alert trigger.	77%	>80%

Table 1: KPIs measurement

modules in one of the test runs of type F2, characterised by a simulated mechanical failure of the bearing (with slowly increasing bearing friction). The figure shows the Health Index evolution along time, which shows the decrease in the HI value from 100 (fully nominal) to 0 (critical condition). The HI starts decreasing after the failure is injected in the simulation. The CLUE alert is triggered about 53 days before the standard FDIR alert. Typically, the Standard FDIR triggers an alert when the friction torque (estimated onboard) reaches a certain value A (used for comparison against the proposed approach) and RW switches off at value B. In this application, the alert threshold value is defined by OHB for the selected RW component: in this case alert threshold A is about half of the value B. It is highlighted that using a lower FDIR alert threshold onboard would lead to higher false alerts rates of the standard FDIR.

Upon CLUE alert, the module also provides the type of failure identified and the RUL estimate. In this case the system detects the bearing mechanical failure (increased friction) and estimates about 22 days to reach a critical condition.

The RUL estimate is updated continuously: for example, when the HI is 50, the updated RUL estimate is of 25 days.

The results of the demonstration tests were promising not only in terms of the KPIs above, related to the correct detection and classification of the alerts by CLUE. What was also considered valuable for operations was the CLUE HI information that provides good insights

into the health status of the AOCS components, ranging from 100 (fully nominal) to 0 (critical condition), in addition to the possibility to identify in advance the incipient failure type and have an evolving estimate of the RUL.

Figure 3: CLUE results.

Finally, the tests carried out also verified that the system is robust to ageing, i.e. it is not triggering alerts when an aged condition of the RW is observed (nominal aged conditions were included in the nominal test dataset, modelled in the simulator). Furthermore, the system triggers a notification of need for retraining when monitoring a different operative condition compared to those used for the training and configuration.

6 Conclusions

This paper presented the results of a project carried out by SATE and OHB System under ESA contract

to show the benefits and feasibility of implementation of innovative AI-based FDIR and prognostics solutions, combining domain knowledge and mature technologies, taking advantage of the experience gathered from the use of these technologies to similar non-space applications.

The results showed that the proposed AI-FDIR solution allows obtaining relevant improvements over the SoA FDIR in terms of:

- Early detection of incipient faults (more than 15 days in advance compared to standard FDIR)
- Early identification of possible root causes (more than 99% accuracy in the discrimination of the different types of failures considered),
- Time to failure prediction (77% accuracy in the prediction of the RUL)

The main features and aspects to be considered to evaluate the impact of the use of the proposed solution in the on-board application scenario, which encompass, among others, hardware related features, solution scalability, improvements and savings over the SoA, maintainability:

- **Architecture optimization:** The proposed architecture may just require potential addition of a co-Processor module within a centralized OBC, without involving additional Unit or harnesses, therefore the overall penalization in terms of mass and power consumption is limited, compared to standard FDIR implementations.
- **Scalability / Growth potential:** Proposed concepts, based on a fully scalable and modular concept as ADHA, offers unlimited scalability.
- **Portability:** The proposed concept is implemented in C code binaries, automatically generated from MATLAB/Simulink for the target application. No dependencies from external libraries are present.
- **Downlink savings:** The proposed concept could allow reducing the number or the data rate of telemetries sent to ground. However, considering that ground systems shall have the possibility to understand the on-board reasoning, the selection of the data shall be duly traded-off.
- **Availability of data for configuration and validation:** The proposed concept implements a reusable workflow for the exploitation of existing simulation models to generate data, to complement historical datasets that may be already available (from same or other satellites of a fleet/constellation).

- **Explainability:** The proposed solution produces enriched information such as Health indexes, Modelled Symptoms, Likelihood of root causes, which supports problems understanding and troubleshooting. Standard FDIR is understandable but cascade alarms are difficult to troubleshoot.
- **Robustness to varying context conditions:** The proposed solution foresees a Model Validity function that assesses the similarity of the input conditions to those in the training set. This allows assessing the robustness / reliability of the output produced. This information is also used by the Self-status check to evaluate need for retraining to properly cover specific conditions. This is not implemented for standard FDIR.
- **Maintainability and reconfigurability:** The proposed concept foresees a Training-over-the-air approach to exploit OPS data labelling by operators, which can even be applied to multiple satellites. Reconfiguration of all system parameters or of the software is granted by design.
- **Scalability:** The proposed solution is applicable to single satellites as well as to fleets or constellations. It has already been used in operation for more than 2 years to fleets of more than 20.000 industrial vehicles.

Acknowledgements

The activity presented in this paper was funded by the European Space Agency. The view expressed in this paper shall in no way be taken to reflect the official opinion of the European Space Agency.

The authors would like to thank ESA, particularly the activity Technical Officer, Luis Mansilla, for his guidance towards our challenging objectives.

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